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Development of milk and dairy production in the food markets of Russia

KEYWORDS

dairy cattle breeding,
milk production,
milk production in the world,
reconstruction and modernization of
dairy cattle breeding facilities

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The topic is relevant because, under the conditions of economic sanctions and instability in international markets, Russia needs to develop its own production of milk and dairy products to reduce dependence on imports and ensure food security.

The article analyzes the prospects of milk and dairy production in Russia's food markets.

Materials and methods. The study materials were periodicals and conference abstracts on trends in the development of the dairy industry and dairy cattle breeding in Russia. Research methods were abstract-logical, monographic, calculative-constructive, comparative, and statistical analysis.

Results. According to FAO data on milk production results in 2020, Russia is in 7th place. In Russia, about 20 thousand agricultural organizations of various forms of ownership with a population of 3.1 million cows are engaged in milk production. In 2021, milk production in all categories of farms amounted to 32.3 million tons, more than 100 thousand tons (+0.3%) compared to the production level of 2020. In the structure of milk production, agricultural organizations account for 55.5%, peasant (farmer) farms – 8.8%, and households – 35.7%. Among the leading regions in milk production is the Volga Federal District. It accounts for almost a third of the total volume of the product – about 9.5 million tons.

The Ministry of Agriculture provides a set of state support measures to stimulate milk production and processing. In 2020, its total volume exceeded 38 billion rubles. In 2021, a comparable level of support volume was provided. In addition, as a stimulus measure during the pandemic period, 10.6 billion rubles were provided to agrarians to reimburse the cost of purchasing fodder for dairy cattle. The key reference point for the industry is the doctrine of food security.

Conclusion. The production of milk and dairy products in the food markets of Russia and the world has significant prospects. Russia has an opportunity to develop the export of dairy products, especially to the CIS countries and the Asia-Pacific region, which can become an additional source of income for producers.

Ibragimov, A. G. (2023). Development of milk and dairy production in the food markets of Russia. *Economic consultant*, (2), 42–53.
<https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2023.2.4>

INTRODUCTION

Dairy products are an important part of the population's diet. With the increase in income and living standards, the demand for quality dairy products is increasing, which creates opportunities for production development. The topic is also relevant due to the fact that in the conditions of economic sanctions and instability in international markets, Russia needs to develop its own production of milk and dairy products to reduce dependence on imports and ensure food security.

The development of dairy production contributes to improving the economic situation in rural areas, creating jobs, and raising farmers' living standards. The introduction of modern technologies in the production of milk and dairy products can improve their quality and competitiveness in the market, which is also an important aspect of the industry's development.

Thus, the topic of developing milk and dairy production in Russia is relevant from both economic and social points of view and requires attention from the state, business, and scientific communities.

The article analyzes the prospects of milk and dairy production in Russia's food markets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials of the study were the data from periodicals and conference abstracts on trends in the development of the dairy industry and dairy cattle breeding in Russia: Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems; Studies in Systems, Decision and Control; Environmental Footprints and Eco-design of Products and Processes; Russian Agricultural Sciences; Transactions on Computer Systems and Networks, Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, and others. The materials of statistical reports of the Russian Federation, its subjects, the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia, and other state bodies, which contain information on the production, consumption, and import of milk and dairy products, were also used. The research used abstract-logical, monographic, calculative-constructive, comparative analysis, and statistical methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The dairy industry plays an important role in the livelihood of many countries. It is the only major sector contributing the most to the global agricultural gross domestic product.

D. Franco and B. G. Nagrale write that the cost of growing milk and the cost of processing dairy products are crucial factors for competitiveness in the global market. The developing and developed countries have structural differences in dairy production, indicating that one common policy for the world is inappropriate [1].

B. E. Bravo-Ureta et al. provide a broad overview of published empirical work on production economics in dairy farming and the prospects for future challenges in this area of research. According to the authors, dairy farming faces serious challenges, especially with respect to environmental sustainability, animal welfare, structural changes, and input-output price volatility [2].

The dairy industry in Russia is an important sector of the agro-industrial complex. It provides domestic and export markets, although a significant portion of milk in the country is supplied for processing. As of 2023, Russia is one of the largest milk producers in the world, but the level of productivity per capita and per head of livestock remains lower than in countries with highly developed dairy industries.

A. B. Malina et al. consider the issues of the country's food security, which is the most important indicator of the state's national security. The authors characterize the dynamics of the total volume of dairy production in Russia, analyze the indicators of export and import of products, and estimate the level of actual consumption of milk and dairy products per capita [3].

The main milk production regions are the Central, North-Western, and Volga Districts.

I. V. Kovaleva et al. write that the dairy industry of the Altai Territory is experiencing a number of difficulties, which are considered through the prism of integration and cooperation processes taking place in the region in particular and in the country as a whole. The authors argue that the current state of affairs is caused by the reduction in the number of dairy herds and, consequently, by the reduction of the raw material base for the regional processing industry [4].

A. E. Suglobov and R. R. Khabipov propose creating consumer purchasing and marketing cooperatives to market milk and dairy products produced by rural residents and farms in the Republic of Tatarstan. The authors propose strengthening the scientific support of these cooperatives to increase their competitiveness [5].

N. N. Shumeiko analyzes the indicators of cow use by breeding organizations of four dairy breeds (Brown Swiss, Holstein, Sychevskaya, and Russian Black-and-White) common in the Smolensk Region. In the author's opinion, productive use is characterized by a decrease in calving age and a decrease in the payback of the dairy herd at its replenishment [6].

A. N. Anishchenko et al. analyze the functioning experience of the dairy subcomplex over the last 17 years in the Vologda Region. According to the authors, the gradual modernization of

economic facilities and technological processes continues, new equipment is purchased, highly qualified personnel are attracted to the enterprises, and livestock productivity is increasing [7].

O. A. Stolyarova et al. consider the dairy subcomplex of the Penza Region. The authors are convinced of the need to develop a national methodology to account for produced and realized milk. In addition, the authors propose a methodology for calculating the purchase price of milk, considering its quality, which will encourage producers to produce better-quality products. The authors conclude that to improve the industry's efficiency, it is necessary to improve the pricing mechanism and develop a concept to help settle the incomes of milk producers and processors [8].

Russia implements many programs and initiatives to support the dairy industry. The main ones are financial subsidies for milk production, support for the construction and modernization of dairy farms, and subsidies for purchasing fodder.

V. I. Chinarov et al. write that state investments aimed at the development of domestic pedigree cattle breeding made it possible to develop a wide network of breeding plants, pedigree reproducers, and gene pool farms throughout the country to meet the needs of agricultural producers in pedigree products. According to the authors, with high annual rates of import substitution of pedigree livestock, the realization of pedigree livestock for six years increased by 62.3%, which allowed the reduction of imports to 15.6% [9].

According to M. A. Grudkina et al., the current system of state support is mainly aimed at compensating for negative factors. State subsidies are not used to introduce innovative technologies in dairy cattle breeding. The authors propose an innovation-oriented mechanism that provides targeted differentiated support for dairy enterprises. The competitive selection of subsidy recipients only supports the most efficient enterprises that introduce resource-saving technologies for dairy production [10].

Rural entrepreneurs' activity is also an important factor in developing the dairy market in Russia.

G. N. Dudukalova et al. analyze the economic and economic activity of various organizational and legal management forms of the country's agro-industrial complex to produce commercial milk and dairy products. The authors formulated a forecast for expanding the nomenclature of trade in milk and milk products. The reasons for the prevalence of imports over exports of milk and dairy products have been revealed [11].

Applying new technologies in the Russian dairy industry covers several key areas: process automation, innovative feed, biotechnology, energy saving, smart farms, product quality, and safety.

According to Y. F. Lachuga and V. V. Kirsanov, the future development of dairy farming should be based on the creation of highly efficient, sustainable, digital, result-oriented

agricultural companies based on the concept of the convergence of nano-bio-information-co-technologies, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence systems [12].

S. M. Nleya and S. Ndlovu write that to mitigate the global hunger problem, the smart dairy farming paradigm utilizes sensors, the Internet of Things, broadband technologies, and data analytics to create innovative solutions and systems. In particular, innovative solutions aim to increase milk yields and improve the efficiency of the milk production process. At the product level, innovation systems seek to increase milk production by deploying robotic milking systems that milk the cow, analyze, process, and store the milk [13].

I. Perov writes that a robotic milking system ensures accurate and timely movement of animals through automated sorting gates between the milking machine, feeding, resting, and special handling areas. According to the author, introducing machine learning techniques will lead to developing risk prediction models to improve animal health and reduce antibiotic use on dairy farms [14].

S. I. Turliy considers the functioning of the dairy-food subcomplex from the perspective of the development directions of its innovative development. The author proposes to improve the mechanisms of distribution of state support, to conduct a competent personnel policy, to increase the information transparency of the industry by specifying the contribution of private subsidiary farms to milk production, and to strengthen control over marketability, quality of breeding material, fodder, raw milk, and herd accounting [15].

Thus, the scientific problem of the development of milk and dairy production in Russia's food markets requires a comprehensive study and solution of a number of interrelated issues that affect the efficiency and sustainability of the dairy industry.

Analysis of production processes. Study of modern technologies and methods of milk and dairy production and their impact on the quality and safety of products. Identifying optimal production practices that can increase efficiency and reduce costs is necessary.

Economic efficiency. An assessment of the economic performance of dairy production, including profitability, cost of production, pricing, and impact on farmer income. Understanding what factors promote or hinder economic growth in this area is important.

Import substitution and competitiveness. Explore opportunities and strategies to reduce dependence on imported dairy products and analyze the competitiveness of domestic producers in domestic and foreign markets.

Social and environmental aspects. To study the impact of dairy production on the social development of rural areas, job creation, and improvement of the quality of life, it is also important to consider the environmental impact of production and the implementation of sustainable practices.

Consumer preferences. Analyze changes in consumer preferences and demand for dairy products, including trends toward healthy eating and organic products. This can help producers adapt their offerings to market demands.

Government support and regulation. Examine the role of government policies, including subsidies, support programs, and product quality regulation, in the development of the dairy sector. Evaluate the effectiveness of existing measures and propose new approaches.

RESULTS

At the end of 2021, world milk production was about 919 million tons, increasing by 1.7% compared to 2020 (see Figure 1). Cow's milk accounts for the major share of the world's milk production [16; 17]. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (hereinafter FAO), cow's milk accounts for 81.1% of the world's total milk production.

Figure 1 Milk production in the world in 2015–2021, million tons

FAO forecasts that world milk production will grow 1.6% per year and increase to 997 million tons by 2029. Butter production is projected to grow at an average annual rate of 1.6%, skim milk powder (SMP) at 1.6% per year, and full cream milk powder (FCMP) at 1.7%. Judging from Figure 1, the linear regression equation is: $y = 19.1071x - 37,695.9286$.

Global per capita consumption of fresh dairy products is projected to increase by 1.0% per annum. In 2020, global dairy exports were valued at approximately \$55.75 billion. International dairy trade increased by 1.2% in 2020, nearly 79 million tons.

The European Union, New Zealand, and the United States will be the top three dairy exporters. These three countries are projected to account for about 65% of cheese exports, 68% of SMP, 76% of butter, and 77% of FCMP exports in 2029 [18; 19].

The development of milk and dairy production is a priority among food markets in Russia. In Russia, about 20 thousand agricultural organizations of various forms of ownership, with 3.1 million cows, are engaged in milk production. According to FAO data on the results of milk production in 2020, Russia is in 7th place. The first place is traditionally India (183.96 million tons of milk), followed by the United States (101.3 million tons), Pakistan (60.8 million tons), China (39.2 million tons), Brazil (36.8 million tons), and Germany (33.2 million tons). In Russia in 2021, milk production in all categories of farms amounted to 32.3 million tons, which is more than 100 thousand tons (+0.3%) compared to the production level in 2020 (see Table 1). In the structure of milk production, agricultural organizations account for 55.5%, peasant (farmer) farms – 8.8%, and households – 35.7% [20].

Table 1

Milk production in Russia in 2018–2021, million tons

Categories of farms	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021 to 2020, %
All categories of farms	30,612	31,360	32,226	32,326	100.3
including: agricultural organizations and peasant (farmer) farms, including individual entrepreneurs	18,756	19,642	20,726	21,056	101.6

The leaders in milk production are six constituent entities of the Russian Federation, each with total milk production of over 1 million tons: the Republic of Tatarstan (1.94 million tons in 2020), the Republic of Bashkortostan (1.67 million tons), the Krasnodar Territory (1.55 million tons), the Altai Territory (1.21 million tons), the Rostov Region (1.10 million tons), and the Voronezh Region (1.02 million tons). Given the continuing positive trend of increasing milk production, there are certain reserves, including at the expense of further growth of milk productivity through fuller utilization of the genetic potential of the dairy herd, creation of a solid fodder base, ensuring the balance of fodder rations, and use of innovative technologies of animal housing. It is estimated that in 2021, the milk yield per cow in agricultural organizations amounted to 6878 kg, which is 150 kg (+2.2%) more than the level of 2020 in farms of all categories – 4939 kg (see Table 2) [21].

Table 2

Milk yield per 1 cow in Russia in 2018-2021, kg

Categories of farms	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021 to 2020, %
All categories of farms	4492	4642	4839	4939	102.1
Including: agricultural organizations	5945	6290	6728	6878	102.2

One of the main factors in increasing milk production is the technical modernization carried out in dairy cattle breeding and the construction of new high-tech dairy farms. According to the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia, 125 dairy cattle farms were built, reconstructed, modernized, and operated in 2021. Additional milk production due to these measures amounted to 521 thousand tons (see Table 3) [21].

Table 3

Commissioned, reconstructed, and modernized facilities for dairy cattle breeding in Russia in 2018–2021

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	Total in 2018-2021
Number of new facilities commissioned	154	122	105	100	481
Number of facilities reconstructed and modernized	85	71	67	25	248
Total:	239	193	172	125	729
Milk production, thousand tons					
Volume of milk production due to new facilities commissioned	267.2	188.1	319.0	474.7	x
Volume of milk production due to reconstruction and modernization	22.6	43.9	41.3	45.9	x
Total	289.8	232	360.3	520.6	x
Number of livestock places created					
due to new facilities commissioned	79,120	75,945	87,995	115,925	358,985
through reconstruction and modernization	14,731	14,688	12,949	8958	51,326
Total	93,851	90,633	100,944	124,883	410,311

The Commission of the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia selected 78 investment projects in dairy cattle breeding for reimbursement of direct incurred costs for the creation and modernization of livestock complexes in 2021, with a total value of 24.8 billion rubles. The

implementation of the selected investment projects made it possible to introduce about 83.5 thousand additional livestock places. The total amount of subsidies due from the federal budget amounted to 5.3 billion rubles. Within the framework of implementation of the State Program of Agriculture Development and Regulation of Markets of Agricultural Products, Raw Materials, and Foodstuffs, milk producers are provided with support aimed at increasing milk productivity, replenishment of working capital within the framework of preferential lending, reimbursement of part of direct incurred costs for construction and modernization of dairy farms, development of pedigree dairy cattle breeding, and other areas.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The production of milk and dairy products in the food markets of Russia and the world has significant prospects. With population growth and changing consumer preferences, there is an increasing demand for dairy products, especially natural and organic ones.

Russia has an opportunity to develop exports of dairy products, especially to CIS countries and the Asia-Pacific region, which may become an additional source of income for producers.

A focus on sustainable production and environmentally friendly technologies can attract the attention of consumers and investors in the context of global climate change and environmental challenges.

Introducing modern technologies in production processes, such as automation, improved livestock genetics, and new processing methods, can improve efficiency and product quality.

Russia has government support programs for agribusiness, including subsidies for dairy farmers, which can help increase production.

Increased interest in local and regional products can contribute to the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in the dairy sector.

Thus, with the right strategy and support from the government and businesses, the development of milk and dairy production in Russia has good prospects.

REFERENCES

1. Franco, D., & Nagrale, B. G. (2020). Dairy Industry: Hurdles Ahead in an Economic Perspective. In: Minj, J., Sudhakaran, V. A., Kumari, A. (eds) Dairy Processing: Advanced Research to Applications. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-2608-4_13

2. Bravo-Ureta, B. E., Wall, A., & Neubauer, F. (2022). Dairy Farming from a Production Economics Perspective: An Overview of the Literature. In: Ray, S. C., Chambers, R. G., Kumbhakar, S. C. (eds) Handbook of Production Economics. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3455-8_31
3. Malina, A. B., Afanaseva, E. P., Kagirova, M. V., & Gafarov, M. R. (2021). Russian Food Security on the Market of Milk and Dairy Products. In: Ashmarina, S., Mantulenko, V., Vochozka, M. (eds) Engineering Economics: Decisions and Solutions from Eurasian Perspective. ENGINEERING ECONOMICS WEEK 2020. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 139. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53277-2_65
4. Kovaleva, I. V., Semina, L. A., & Semikolenova, M. N. (2021). The Effective Functioning of the Dairy Industry in the Conditions of Integration and Cooperation. In: Bogoviz, A. V., Ragulina, J. V. (eds) Industry Competitiveness: Digitalization, Management, and Integration. ISCI 2019. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 280. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80485-5_13
5. Suglobov, A. E., & Khabipov, R. R. (2022). Regional Economic Policy in Dairy Production. In: Bogoviz, A. V., Suglobov, A. E., Maloletko, A. N., Kaurova, O. V. (eds) Cooperation and Sustainable Development. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 245. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77000-6_165
6. Shumeiko, N. N. (2021). Productive Use of Cows in Dairy Cattle Breeding. In: Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) The Challenge of Sustainability in Agricultural Systems. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 206. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72110-7_93
7. Anishchenko, A. N., Usmanov, D. I., Zadumkin, K. A. (2021). Modernization of the Regional Dairy Product Subcomplex in the Framework of Import Substitution Policies. In: Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) Complex Systems: Innovation and Sustainability in the Digital Age. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control, vol 283. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58823-6_36
8. Stolyarova, O. A., Vinnichuk, L. B., & Reshetkina, Y. V. (2022). Improving the Price Mechanism in Milk Production and Processing. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) Sustainable Agriculture. Environmental Footprints and Eco-design of Products and Processes. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8731-0_35
9. Chinarov, V. I., Shemetyuk, S. A., Bautina, O. V., Chinarov, A. V., & Azhmyakov, A. A. (2022). Problems of Managing Large-Scale Breeding in Russian Cattle Breeding. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) Sustainable Agriculture. Environmental Footprints and Eco-design of Products and Processes. Springer,

- Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8731-0_13
10. Grudkina, M. A., Grudkina, T. I., & Kravchenko, T. S. (2021). Innovation-Oriented Government Support of Agricultural Industry. In: Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) *The Challenge of Sustainability in Agricultural Systems. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 206. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72110-7_50
 11. Dudukalova, G. N., Tkach, A. V., Nechitaylov, A. S. (2020). The Development of the Dairy Market in Russia. In: Bogoviz, A. (eds) *Complex Systems: Innovation and Sustainability in the Digital Age. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, vol 282. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44703-8_47
 12. Lachuga, Y. F., & Kirsanov, V. V. (2021). Analysis of Cyclicity in Technique and Technology Evolution across Different Technological Paradigms with the Example of the Dairy Industry. *Russian Agricultural Sciences*, 47, 283–289. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1068367421030113>
 13. Nleya, S. M., & Ndlovu, S. (2021). Smart Dairy Farming Overview: Innovation, Algorithms and Challenges. In: Choudhury, A., Biswas, A., Singh, T. P., Ghosh, S. K. (eds) *Smart Agriculture Automation Using Advanced Technologies. Transactions on Computer Systems and Networks*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6124-2_3
 14. Perov, I. (2022). Robotic Dairy Systems—Change in Management Paradigm. In: Ronzhin, A., Berns, K., Kostyaev, A. (eds) *Agriculture Digitalization and Organic Production. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, vol. 245. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3349-2_2
 15. Turliy, S. I. (2021). Innovative-Based Development of the Dairy and Food Subcomplex of the Agro-Industrial Complex. In: Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) *The Challenge of Sustainability in Agricultural Systems. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 205. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73097-0_38
 16. Ibragimov, A. G. (2022). Ways to increase economic efficiency of feed utilization in animal breeding. Moscow.
 17. Ibragimov, A. G. (2019). To the question of effective land use in Russia. *Ekonomika i predprinimatelstvo = Economics and entrepreneurship*, 110 (9), 1316–1319.
 18. Ibragimov, A. G. (2013). Ecological and economic assessment of the effectiveness of the use of waste processing of agricultural products. Moscow.
 19. Olgarenko, D. G. (2017). State and prospects for the development of water management complex of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2020. In collection: *Modern directions in agro-economic science Timiryazevka. Scientific edition*. Moscow, 314–317.

20. Platonovsky, N. G. (2021). Green Economy in Russia and the World: Status and Prospects. *Economics of Agriculture in Russia*, (9), 103–108.
21. Platonovsky, N. G. (2021). Efficiency of the Russian dairy industry. Scientific and analytical review. Moscow.

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Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/06/01/ibragimov-3/>

Received: Dec 25, 2022 | **Accepted:** Feb 20, 2023 | **Published:** Jun 1, 2023

Editor: Daniela Antonescu, PhD in Economics. Romanian Academy, ROMANIA

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Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.